

Complexes of Cerium(III), Thorium(IV) and Dioxouranium(II) with 8-(Arylazo)-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin Dyes

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Manuscript received 26 December 1991, accepted 19 March 1992

Proton-ligand ionisation and metal-ligand stability constants of 8-(arylazo)-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin complexes with Ce^{III}, Th^{IV} and UO₂^{II} ions have been determined pH-metrically in 60% (v/v) ethanol-water mixture at 25° and $\mu = 0.1$. The order of stability constants was found to be Th^{IV} > Ce^{III} > UO₂^{II} 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 (M : L) complexes are formed as evidenced by conductimetric studies. The complexes have been isolated in solid state and characterised on the basis of elemental analyses, thermal, ir and nmr spectral data.

Coumarin derivatives are of interest because of their physiological, photodynamic and bacteriostatic activity¹. Besides, they have been found to have several important analytical uses². El-Ansary *et al.*³ studied the emission and excitation spectra of some new coumarin azo dyes. They also carried out potentiometric, conductimetric and spectrophotometric studies⁴⁻⁷ on hydroxy coumarin, and their metal chelates. The present communication deals with the evaluation of the proton, Ce^{III}, Th^{IV} and UO₂^{II} ligand formation constants of some 8-(arylazo)-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin dyes (1). The structure of the solid complexes was also investigated by elemental analyses, thermal, ir and nmr spectroscopy studies.

Results and Discussion

The proton-ligand formation constants values (Table 1) are in agreement with those previously reported⁶.

The formation curves of the complexes were obtained by plotting the average number of ligands attached per metal ion (\bar{n}) versus the free ligand exponent (pL). The maximum \bar{n} values calculated for the metal-ligand system were found not to exceed two, indicating the formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 (metal : ligand) complexes. The mean log β_1 and log β_2 values for the chelates are listed in Table 1. It is to be mentioned that log β_1 and log β_2 values for all the complexes are higher in case of 1k than those obtained in case of other ligands. This may be attributed to the existence of the two OH groups *ortho* with respect to the azo group resulting the formation of a solochrome like structure (*o,o'*-dihydroxyazo) which is known by its high stability constant as a result of the formation of more than one stable chelate ring. It is obvious that the stability constants of the different complexes follow the order : Th^{IV} > Ce^{III} > UO₂^{II}, i.e. the stability of these complexes increases with increasing charge on the metal ion⁸.

The conductimetric titration curves for the complexes show two breaks at molar ratios of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 indicating the formation of two types of complexes with stoichiometric ratios 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 (M : L), which is in accordance with the results obtained from pH-metric titrations and also with the actual isolation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 (M : L) solid complex species. The titration curves indicate a gradual increase in the conductance values due to the displacement of protons from the ligand on complex formation⁹.

The results of elemental analysis¹⁰ (Table 2) are in good agreement with those required by the suggested formulae. Also, it is to be mentioned that in all cases 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 (M : L) solid chelates were isolated.

The mode of bonding of the ligands (1b, i and k) to the metal ions was elucidated by recording the ir and nmr spectra of the complexes as compared with those of the free ligands.

Ir spectra : The broad weak band observed at 3 500 cm⁻¹ (OH) in the spectra of the free ligands shifted to lower wavenumber (~3 400 cm⁻¹) in the complexes. This behaviour may be attributed to the participation of the OH group in chelation with metal ions and the new band is due to coordinated water molecules. The δ_{OH} band observed at lower wavenumber with increase in intensity, is due to the liberation of the OH groups from hydrogen bond formation through chelation with the metal ions. The band at 1 090 cm⁻¹ ν_{C-OH} is observed at more or less the same position with respect to chelates with 1b and 1i ligands but not with 1k. This may be taken as an evidence for involvement of OH group in chelation. With 1k ligand, the band appears at nearly the same position with its intensity and this may be due to the existence of non-ionised one OH group in all cases.

The ν_{CO} band is observed at its position with the same intensity for 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes while for the 1 : 1 complexes with UO₂^{II} three adjacent

TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANTS FOR METAL COMPLEXES WITH LIGANDS (1a - m)

Compd. no.	H			Th ^{IV}		Ce ^{III}		UO ₂ ^{II}	
	pK ₁	pK ₂	pK ₃	log β ₁	log β ₂	log β ₁	log β ₂	log β ₁	log β ₂
1a	6.22	10.53	—	9.39	17.54	8.74	16.26	7.08	12.25
b	5.92	10.47	—	9.37	16.73	8.24	15.75	7.51	13.06
c	6.49	10.36	—	9.77	17.92	9.33	17.79	8.01	15.32
d	6.93	9.77	—	9.50	17.67	9.06	16.22	7.38	13.99
e	5.44	10.40	—	8.86	17.02	8.00	13.74	6.98	12.96
f	8.13	10.63	—	11.43	21.61	11.22	20.84	9.56	18.29
g	7.54	10.63	—	10.96	21.17	10.93	21.09	9.27	18.04
h ^a	7.71	10.62	—	11.16	20.85	10.52	19.81	7.80	14.19
i ^b	7.66	10.71	—	10.79	19.72	10.53	18.79	8.59	15.54
j	8.02	10.42	12.30	12.85	24.25	12.67	23.74	10.14	19.22
k	7.04	10.91	11.90	13.73	26.11	13.65	25.78	11.02	21.23
l	8.22	10.76	—	11.98	22.36	11.20	22.34	10.61	19.02
m	6.25	10.54	—	9.63	18.17	9.42	17.66	7.77	14.20

^apK_{COOH}=5.11. ^bpK_{COOH}=6.51.

TABLE 2—ELEMENTAL DATA OF METAL CHELATES WITH LIGANDS 1b, 1i AND 1k

Ligand	Complex	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				
		C	H	M	Cl	Metal
<i>Thorium</i>						
1b	(1 : 1) [Th(C ₁₆ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₄ Cl).Cl ₂ .2H ₂ O]	27.93 (27.90)	2.05 (2.11)	4.07 (4.00)	20.61 (20.58)	33.72 (33.65)
1b	(1 : 2) [Th(C ₁₆ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₄ Cl) ₂ .2H ₂ O]2Cl	39.77 (39.68)	2.50 (2.48)	5.80 (5.76)	14.67 (14.63)	24.91 (24.85)
1i	(1 : 1) [Th(C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₄).2H ₂ O.2Cl]Cl	29.27 (29.25)	2.17 (2.13)	4.02 (4.06)	15.24 (15.22)	33.26 (33.19)
1i	(1 : 2) [Th(C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₄) ₂ .2H ₂ O]2Cl	41.44 (41.40)	2.66 (2.65)	5.68 (5.63)	7.19 (7.16)	23.54 (23.51)
1k	(1 : 1) [Th(C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₄).Cl ₂ .2H ₂ O]Cl	28.70 (28.66)	2.26 (2.23)	4.18 (4.16)	15.88 (15.83)	34.65 (34.58)
1k	(1 : 2) [Th(C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₄) ₂ .2H ₂ O]2Cl	41.35 (41.32)	2.82 (2.79)	6.03 (6.00)	7.63 (7.59)	24.96 (24.92)
<i>Cerium</i>						
1b	(1 : 1) [Ce(C ₁₆ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₄ Cl).2NO ₃ .2H ₂ O]	31.30 (31.36)	2.30 (2.30)	9.13 (9.18)	5.77 (5.82)	22.82 (22.90)
1b	(1 : 2) [Ce(C ₁₆ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₄ Cl) ₂ .H ₂ O.OH]	47.88 (47.76)	2.89 (2.86)	6.98 (7.02)	8.83 (8.75)	17.40 (17.42)
1i	(1 : 1) [Ce(C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₄).2NO ₃ .2H ₂ O]	30.81 (30.90)	2.28 (2.32)	8.46 (8.50)	—	21.16 (21.12)
1i	(1 : 2) [Ce(C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₄) ₂ .H ₂ O.OH]	49.70 (49.66)	3.07 (3.11)	6.81 (6.70)	—	17.05 (16.93)
1k	(1 : 1) [Ce(C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₄).2NO ₃ .2H ₂ O]	32.27 (33.28)	2.54 (2.56)	9.41 (9.43)	—	23.53 (23.48)
1k	(1 : 2) [Ce(C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₄) ₂ .H ₂ O.OH]	50.20 (50.18)	3.29 (3.26)	7.32 (7.28)	—	18.30 (18.25)
<i>Uranium</i>						
1b	(1 : 1) [UO ₂ (C ₁₆ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₄ Cl).CH ₃ COO.2H ₂ O]	31.85 (31.78)	2.52 (2.72)	4.13 (4.10)	5.22 (5.18)	35.07 (35.00)
1b	(1 : 2) [UO ₂ (C ₁₆ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₄ Cl) ₂ .2H ₂ O]	41.17 (41.12)	2.59 (2.62)	6.00 (6.08)	7.57 (7.48)	25.50 (25.62)
1i	(1 : 1) [UO ₂ (C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₄).CH ₃ COO.2H ₂ O]	31.96 (31.82)	2.68 (2.65)	4.14 (4.08)	—	35.20 (35.12)
1i	(1 : 2) [UO ₂ (C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₄) ₂ .2H ₂ O]	42.85 (42.92)	2.75 (2.83)	5.88 (5.76)	—	25.00 (24.88)
1k	(1 : 1) [UO ₂ (C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₄).CH ₃ COO.2H ₂ O]	32.74 (32.68)	2.75 (2.73)	4.24 (4.21)	—	36.05 (35.96)
1k	(1 : 2) [UO ₂ (C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₄) ₂ .2H ₂ O]	44.43 (44.66)	3.03 (3.14)	6.48 (6.51)	—	27.54 (27.66)

bands are observed at lower wavenumber, which are attributed to the existence of the acetate ions¹¹ as confirmed by the results of elemental analysis. The $\nu_{N=N}$ band (1420 cm⁻¹) exhibits a slight shift to lower wavenumber values which may be taken as

evidence for the participation of the N=N group in chelation.

The participation of the coumarin hydroxylic group in chelation rather than the phenolic OH

group in case of **1k** ligand is gathered from the shift of the C=O band under the influence of coordination (charge migration from the coumarin ring) leading to decrease the polarity of the C=O group.

Nmr spectra : For UO_2^{II} and Th^{IV} 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 chelates, the signals at δ 3.0–4.0 were not present in the spectra of the free ligand, indicating the presence of H_2O molecules in these complexes.

For UO_2^{II} -**1b** 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 chelates, the disappearance of the OH signal at δ 6.3 compared with that of the free ligand, indicating the participation of OH group in chelate formation. For UO_2^{II} -**1i** 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 chelates, the signal appearing at δ 6.2 for 1 : 1 with integration value indicates one proton and that for 1 : 2 indicates two protons, attributed to COOH.

For UO_2^{II} - and Th^{IV} -**1k** 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 chelates, the integration curves show one OH proton in position-7 for 1 : 1 at δ 6.1 and two OH protons for 1 : 2 at 6.3 ppm.

On the other hand, the variation associated to the signals at δ 7.0–8.0, which are assigned to the aromatic protons, indicates that the chelation disturbs to some extent the electron density distribution through the coumarin moiety.

Thermal analysis : From the TGA curves obtained for the uranyl complexes, the weight loss for each complex was calculated within the temperature range at which the coordinated water molecules were expelled. The loss below 100° is attributed to the moisture and the hygroscopic water, since the formed chelates are hygroscopic in nature. The number of coordinated water molecules are two per chelate molecule as indicated from TGA curves. The results obtained are in agreement with the theoretical values. For 1 : 1 chelates, two water molecules are coordinated to the metal ion to fulfil the coordination number eight and they were expelled in the temperature range 100 – 250° . Also, for 1 : 2 chelates, two water molecules are coordinated per each chelate molecule and they were removed at 110 – 280° . It is difficult to use the percent of the residue in uranyl chelates to calculate the metal content from TGA results and this is due to the complexity of the residue.

Based on the above results, uranyl chelates (1 : 1) show the coordination number eight. The first two coordination sites are occupied by the replacement of proton of the hydroxyl group in position-7 and by coordination to nitrogen of the azo group. The remaining six sites are occupied by two water molecules coordinated together with ligand molecule in the plane, while the two oxygen atoms of the uranyl group are perpendicular to the plane and two bonds from one acetate radical to neutralise the charge of the metal ion. For uranyl chelates (1 : 2), the coordination sites are occupied as follows : two covalent bonds supported by the two hydroxyl groups, two coordinate bonds supported by two nitrogens of the azo groups, the other four sites are filled by two water molecules coordinated

together with ligand molecule in the plane, while the two oxygen atoms of the uranyl group are perpendicular to the plane.

Experimental

All reagents used were of the highest purity grade (B.D.H.). The azo dyes (**1**) were prepared as previously recommended⁷ and crystallised from ethanol or acetic acid. The resulting ligands were confirmed by their reported m.p. and elemental analyses.

where X is : H (**1a**), *p*-Cl (**1b**), *p*-Br (**1c**), *p*-I (**1d**), *p*-NO₂ (**1e**), *p*-CH₃ (**1f**), *p*-OCH₃ (**1g**), *p*-COOH (**1h**), *o*-COOH (**1i**), *p*-OH (**1j**), *o*-OH (**1k**), *p*-SO₃H (**1l**) and *p*-N(CH₃)₂ (**1m**)

Stock ligand solutions (0.001 *M*) were prepared in absolute ethanol. 0.01 *M* solutions of Ce^{III}-nitrate, Th^{IV}-chloride and UO₂^{II}-acetate were prepared and standardised by recommended methods¹², and then 0.001 *M* solutions were prepared by dilution. Solutions of 0.100 *N* and 0.200 *N* KOH, 0.100 *N* HCl and 1.0 *M* NaCl were also prepared in double-distilled water.

The determination of proton- and metal-ligand stability constants were determined at 25° as previously described¹³.

Conductimetric titrations were performed using a CM-1K conductivity meter.

The solid complexes were prepared as previously described⁵ and stored in a vacuum desiccator for several days and subjected to elemental microanalysis at the microanalytical centre, Cairo University. The ir spectra (KBr) of the free ligand and metal complexes were recorded on a Pye-Unicam SP 3-300 spectrophotometer and nmr spectra on a Varian-Gimini (200 MHz) spectrometer. The thermogravimetric analysis was performed using a Shimadzu-DT-30 analyser. The weight loss was measured from the ambient temperature up to 500° at a rate of $10^\circ/\text{min}$.

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